

TECHNICAL REPORT: INITIAL DESIGN OF THE REG-RAD CONCEPT

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Glossary

Acronym	Signification
AMC	Aircraft Mission Calculator
CPACS	COMMON PARAMETRIC AIRCRAFT CONFIGURATION SCHEMA
EIS	Entry into Service
REG-BAS	Regional Base (reference aircraft)
REG-RAD	Regional Radical
TLAR	Top Level Aircraft Requirements

1. INTRODUCTION

The current document provides an overview of the regional-radical (REG-RAD) design, modelled by the DLR for the initial design loop of IMOTHEP.

For more information about IMOTHEP project, please check: <https://www.imothep-project.eu/>.

2. DESIGN EXPLORATION RESULTS REG-RAD AIRCRAFT (DLR)

The regional hybrid-electric aircraft configuration investigated by DLR is identified as REG-RAD. It is based on a conventional twin-turboshaft propulsion architecture similar to the existing ATR 42-600. The first loop of the hybrid electric exploration for this REG-RAD configuration is focused on a distributed electric propulsion system. Subsequent loops are planned to also include a hybrid energy storage approach using the distributed propulsion configuration as a base.

2.1. SPECIFIC DESIGN TOOLS

The following tools were used:

- openAD – DLR-internal Tool for overall aircraft design [1].
- AMC (Aircraft Mission Calculator) – DLR-internal Tool for mission performance calculation. (no publication on that yet)

Both tools are integrated into a CPACS [2] based Mass-Pefo-Loop workflow in RCE [3], in which the input/output of the tool converges.

The workflow set-up is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overall aircraft design workflow used for the REG-RAD model.

The model was calibrated to reproduce the results of the REG-BAS model. Calibration on the ATR42 was skipped for the reason that the REG-BAS has already been calibrated on the ATR42. Hence, a calibration on the REG-BAS implicitly includes a calibration on the ATR42 combined with an alignment on the technology level assumed for the REG-BAS. The calibrated model was subsequently modified for calculating a distributed propulsion configuration with a partially turboelectric chain - the REG-RAD concept.

2.2. INITIAL DESIGN OF THE REG-RAD

This section concentrates on the REG-RAD configuration, featuring a distributed propulsion system with 8 electrically driven propellers, as opposed to the classical twin-turboprop configuration of the REG-REF and REG-BAS aircraft.

Figure 2: Overview of the general arrangement of REG-RAD-HEP configuration.

The TLARs that have been used for the sizing is given in Table 1.

The results of the aircraft sizing are shown in Table 2, which shows an overview of the REG-RAD top-level aircraft parameters.

Table 1 Overview of the TLARs considered for the REG-RAD configuration

PARAMETER	UNITS	VALUE
Year of Entry into Service (EIS)	-	2035+
Design Range	nm	600
Design Cruise Mach Number	-	0.48
Design Cruise Altitude	ft	20000
Service Ceiling	ft	20000
Takeoff Balanced Field Length	m	1100
One Engine Inoperative Ceiling (ISA Conditions)	ft	15000
Approach Speed (Calibrated Airspeed)	kts	115
Number of Passengers (Standard Layout)	-	40
Design Mission Payload	kg	4240
Max Payload	kg	4876

Table 2 Overall aircraft characteristics of the REG-RAD design.

AIRCRAFT	UNITS	RESULTS
GEOMETRY		
Wing Ref. Area	m ²	48.6
Wing Span	m	26.1
Wing Aspect Ratio	-	14.0
HTP Ref. Area	m ²	12.8
VTP Ref. Area	m ²	14.74
Fuselage Length	m	22.7
Fuselage Width	m	2.85
Fuselage Height	m	2.72
PROPULSION		
Propulsion Architecture Type		Partially Turboelectric
Propeller Diameter	m	2.60
Total Installed Power (SL, ISA)	kW	2505
Sea-Level Static Thrust (ISA)	kN	68.5
SYSTEMS		
System Architecture		Similar to ATR 42
Engine Offtakes Type		Conventional
DESIGN MASSES		
Max. Takeoff Weight	kg	16637
Max. Landing Weight	kg	16512
Max. Zero-Fuel Weight	kg	15384
Operating Empty Weight	kg	10508
Max. Fuel Weight	kg	3859
Design Fuel Weight	kg	1913
Design Payload	kg	4240
LOW-SPEED PERFO		
CL _{max} Takeoff	-	2.50
CL _{max} Landing	-	2.64
Approach Speed (Calibrated Airspeed)	kts	115
V ₂ - Second Segment Calibrated Airspeed	kts	103

The following mass breakdown for the REG-RAD design has been generated:

Table 3 Mass breakdown for the REG-RAD design.

Component Breakdown	Mass	xCoG
Units	[kg]	[m]
Wing	1541	12.264
Fuselage Structure	2440	12.150
HTP	198	26.319
VTP	255	25.018
Pylon	0	0
Landing Gear	536	11.226
<i>Main Gear</i>	440	12.946
<i>Nose Gear</i>	95	3.277
Engine	2307	10.492
<i>Propeller</i>	286	-
<i>Nacelle</i>	269	-
<i>Gas Turbine & Gearbox</i>	558	-
<i>Hybrid Chain</i>	862	-
<i>Eng & Nacelle Systems</i>	181	-
Systems	1610	9.018
<i>Flight Controls</i>	180	-
<i>Instruments</i>	80	-
<i>Hydraulic Systems</i>	160	-
<i>APU</i>	0	-
<i>Electrical Systems</i>	550	-
<i>Avionics</i>	230	-
<i>Air Cond. & De-Icing</i>	380	-
<i>Fire Protection</i>	30	-
Furnishings	920	13.100
Manuf. Empty Weight (MWE)	9808	11.816
Operating Items	700	13.100
Operating Empty Weight (OWE)	10508	11.902
Max. Payload	4876	13.500
Max. Fuel	3859	11.906
Max. Zero-Fuel Weight (MZFW)	15384	12.408
Max. Landing Weight (MLW)	16512	12.381
Max. Takeoff Weight (MTOW)	16637	12.377

The hybrid propulsion architecture is shown in Figure 3.

The current hybrid components assumptions are:

- Emotor + Inverter + Cooling + Power Feed System = 5 kW/kg (with respect to output power)
- Generator + Rectifier + Cooling + Power Distribution System = 7 kW/kg (with respect to input power)
- Total efficiency: 90%

The assumptions are a preliminary “best guess” estimate based on findings from previous projects.

Figure 3: Overview of the hybrid chain arrangement.

The takeoff constraint assumes the same static thrust-to-weight ratio as the REG-BAS. The bigger propeller area (compared to the REG-BAS) combined with this assumption results in a lower installed power requirement. This might lead to overall takeoff performance penalty. However, the blown-wing lift boost will have a positive effect, as the lift-off speed will be decreased. It remains to be checked whether the takeoff performance TLAR can be fulfilled with the current power level – this analysis needs low-speed prop / aero results. This has not been evaluated in the Task 1.3 work and would ideally be addressed in a later stage in the Task 1.4 evaluations in the subsequent loops.

No low-speed effect of the blown wing during approach is considered – an identical $C_{L,max,Landing}$ to the baseline is assumed. The approach speed TLAR is sizing the wing area. Since it is assumed that the max. lift coefficient during approach does not increase with blown wing, the wing loading in approach (MLM / S_{ref} – max. landing mass divided by wing reference area) remains unchanged with respect to the baseline. Ultimately, this results in a bigger wing, as REG-RAD is heavier than REG-BAS due to the hybrid chain.

The maximum lift coefficient during take-off is assumed 15% higher than for the reference aircraft (tbc), which results in a lower second segment speed. The second segment speed is an important parameter for the propeller design.

The propellers should be able to provide adequate performance (“adequate” is to be defined) at:

- Sea Level, ISA, $Ma = 0.167$, prop shaft power = 313 kW.
- 15000ft, ISA+10°C (true airspeed > calibrated airspeed), $Ma = 0.222$ – this point is from the OEI Ceiling TLAR. Prop shaft power = 313kW.
- Cruise performance should still be with a higher priority for the propeller design.

2.3. DESIGN MISSION BREAKDOWN

The design mission trajectory is plotted in Figure 4. A breakdown of the design mission is provided in Table 4.

Figure 4: Overview of the mission trajectory and the power profile per e-motor (identical for all eight e-motors).

Table 4 Overview of the design mission summary.

Segment	mFuel [kg]	Time [min]	Dist [km]	alt0 [m]	alt1 [m]	Ma0 [-]	Ma1 [-]
Taxi_out	23	5.0	0.0	0	0	0.00	0.00
Take_off	25	1.5	0.0	0	457	0.00	0.31
Climb	273.3	22.4	164.9	457	6096	0.31	0.44
acceleration	30.5	2.8	25.5	6096	6096	0.44	0.48
Cruise	935.4	93.1	847.6	6096	6096	0.48	0.48
Deceleration	0.4	0.2	1.4	6096	6096	0.48	0.46
Descent	19.4	9.1	71.8	6096	457	0.46	0.34
App&lan	22.1	5.0	0.0	457	0	0.34	0.00
Taxi_in	16	3.0	0.0	0	0	0.00	0.00
Main Mission	1345.1	142.1	1111.2				
Go_around	25	1.0	0.0	0	457	0.00	0.25
Div. Climb	113.5	8.9	49.8	457	4880	0.25	0.31
Div. Acceleration	1.8	0.2	1.0	4880	4880	0.31	0.33
Div. Cruise	59.4	8.9	56.6	4880	4880	0.33	0.33
Div. Deceleration	0.4	0.2	1.1	4880	4880	0.33	0.31
Div. Descent	32.2	13.8	76.7	4880	457	0.31	0.25
Div. Acceleration	5.7	0.4	2.5	457	457	0.25	0.30
Div. Holding	257.4	30.0	0.0	457	457	0.30	0.30
Div. App&lan	22.5	5.0	0.0	457	0	0.30	0.00
Contingency	65.3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Reserves	583.2	68.3	187.7				

2.4. COMPARISON TO REG-REF AND REG-BAS

The current concept has been designed to serve as a starting point for the other work-packages with a focus on distributed propulsion. In this initial loop, the gas turbines are the only power providers for the concept. The concept does not yet take into account advantages for the high-lift system, empennage sizing or wing mass effects. Currently only the mass and efficiency penalty of the hybrid chain is modelled. The concept also does not take advantage of any opportunities for hybridizing the energy storage, e.g. introducing a battery.

Even with the advantage of flying at a higher cruise altitude, the current design is less fuel-efficient than REG-BAS, which can be seen in Table 5. However, since none of the potential advantages of distributing the propellers (except the increase in propeller disk area) have been modelled for the current concept, the performance comparison with REG-REF and REG-BAS is not representative for the potential of the configuration.

Table 5 Mission fuel comparison between REG-REF, REG-BAS, and REG-RAD.

Parameter	Unit	REG-REF	REG-BAS	REG-RAD
Design Mission Range	nm	600	600	600
Cruise altitude	ft	15000	15000	20000
Cruise Mach	-	0.48	0.48	0.48
Design Mission Fuel	kg	2314	1822	1912
Typical Mission Fuel (200nm)	kg	1227	969	1042

The modelling of the advantages of the configuration is planned for the next loop in the Task 1.4 evaluations.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS

Modelling limitations:

- A generic gas turbine map.
- A generic propeller map.
- A generic aerodynamic map.
- No aerodynamic effect modelling of the blown wing configuration for final landing approach (which sizes the wing area).
- Generic assumptions for the electric components.

The next loop is planned to use a higher-fidelity modelling input for the mentioned limitations from the other WPs.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] PRELIMINARY AIRCRAFT DESIGN WITHIN A MULTI-DISCIPLINARY AND MULTI-FIDELITY DESIGN ENVIRONMENT. Wöhler, Sebastian, et al.; Bordeaux 2020. Aerospace Europe Conference.
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